

COMPRESSION RESISTANCE OF MOSO BAMBOO INFECTED BY THE LONGHORN BEETLE CHLOROPHORUS ANNULARIS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the lifecycle behavior of the longhorn beetle *Chlorophorus annularis*, one of the main insects that damage dried bamboo culms in Brazil. Damaged culms infected by the beetle and healthy culms were investigated for comparison of their physical and mechanical properties. Mechanical tests were realized on samples of Moso bamboo (*Phyllostachys edulis*) under compression forces using Controls 50-C46Z00/MCC8 Multitest equipment. The tests demonstrated the loss of resistance of the infected bamboo culms according to the degree of infection of the analyzed samples in comparison with the healthy bamboo culms.

KEYWORDS

Moso bamboo, *Phyllostachys edulis*, *Chlorophorus annularis*, longhorn beetle, compression resistance

INTRODUCTION

Bamboo is a plant of the *Poaceae* family, native from Asia, Africa, and America. From the total of 1,100 bamboo species reported in the literature and of 65 genres of bamboos known in the world, the Americas have 31% of the genres and 39% of the species (Judziewicz et al., 1999). Brazil is home to 258 species of endemic bamboo distributed in 35 genres and 2 tribes: *Olyreae* (herbaceous bamboo) and *Bambuseae* (woody bamboo) (Drumond & Wiedman, 2017). Bamboo is a non-timber renewable resource that grows faster than any other plant on Earth. The culm reaches its final size in approximately 3 months and its maximum mechanical properties between 3 and 4 years old. The basic structure of the bamboo plant consists of a lignocellulosic composite of a ramifying system of vegetative axes, which are composed of roots, rhizomes, culms, branches, and leaves (CBRC, 2001). Bamboo culms present a conic and cylindrical geometry, reinforced by transversal nodes, and can be used as a sustainable building material for several technical applications. The anatomical structure of the culm consists of about 50% cellulose, 40% fibers, and 10% conducting tissue, which varies with species (Krause et al., 2016). Bamboo presents a pattern of alternated nodes and hollow internodes. Fibers are distributed in the cross-section showing the increase of their volumetric fraction from the inner to the outer part of the culm wall. Bamboo is a functionally graded composite biomaterial (FGCM) at macro, meso, micro, and nanoscales (Ghavami et al., 2003). Research programs conducted in Brazil have obtained and reported the physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms with industrial potential (Navarro, 2011; Tan et al., 2011; Seixas et al., 2021). Although the recent advances in the application of bamboo as an engineering material, an effective and eco-friendly manner of treatment bamboo culms remain a lack. The treatment methods utilized for the preservation of bamboo poles can be subdivided into two main groups, known as physical and chemical treatments (Hidalgo-López, 2003). Physical treatments have the intent to remove water and starch from the culms, making bamboo less susceptible to fungal and pests' attacks. They are cheaper and less pollutant than chemical treatments, but their efficiency is not guaranteed. On the other hand, chemical treatments consist to fill the bamboo culm wall with toxic

preservatives, avoiding the occurrence of fungi and insects. Chemical treatments utilized for bamboo are more specialized, needing industrialized procedures and the use of pollutant chemicals, requiring specific processes to do not contaminate the environment and workers involved in the procedure. Several methods for the treatment of bamboo poles have been developed to increase the durability of bamboo (Barak et al., 2009; Yu et al., 2010; Pandoli et al., 2015). Different factors can improve the durability of bamboo, for example, the choice of the bamboo species, the selection of the poles on the plantation with the age of approximately 5 years, the treatment, and climate factors that involve the application of bamboo species. All of these factors can increase or reduce the durability of the material, considering its wide range of applications, from craftsmen to industrial uses. Some methods used to preserve bamboo culms are more pollutant, such as the Boucherie treatment that uses arsenic in its formulation. Other treatments are less pollutant, as the immersion of the culms on a solution using sodium borate with water (Hidalgo-López, 1981). Even nowadays, sustainable techniques for the treatment of bamboo culms with effective results, economic viability, and low environmental impact are a great challenge for building with bamboo. In the past 15 years, an insect named *Chlorophorus annularis* (*Fabricius*) started to be observed in dried bamboo culms in Brazil. The presence of this insect could be perceived because it damages the structure of the bamboo culm during the lifecycle of the borer, reducing the mechanical properties of the bamboo culms. The larvae create channels inside the bamboo culm wall during the stages from larvae to pupae and a hole in the external part of the culm when the adult borer goes to the external environment. The objective of this paper is to report the results of an experimental program carried out at the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio) intending to investigate the lifecycle of the longhorn beetle *Chlorophorus annularis* and the compressive performance of dried *Phyllostachys edulis* bamboo infected by this insect. Concentric compression tests were realized on both healthy and infected Moso bamboo samples for the evaluation of the degree of the attack by the longhorn beetle and its influence on the reduction of the mechanical properties of dried Moso bamboo culms.

THE LONGHORN BEETLE CHLOROPHORUS ANNULARIS

Different species of insects that infect bamboo culms have been reported in the literature (Alexander et al., 2019). One of these species named *Chlorophorus annularis* (*Fabricius*) was considered a species with high pest risk potential to the international bamboo trade and the building industry utilizing round pole bamboo (Yu et al., 2010). Methods for the treatment of bamboo stems have been studied to control the dissemination of bamboo borers worldwide (Gardner, 1945; Wang et al., 2019; Weifeng et al., 2016). *Chlorophorus annularis* (*Fabricius*) is an insect endemic from Asia, mainly found in China, India, and Indonesia (Hill, 2008). *C. annularis* is a longhorn beetle from the Cerambycidae family, Chrysomeloidea superfamily, and Coleoptera order. According to (Jackson et al., 2006), the presence of *C. annularis* has been observed on dried bamboo culms of *Bambusa spp.*, *Bambusa multiplex*, *Bambusa tulda*, *Bambusa vulgaris*, *Bambusa spinosa*, *Dendrocalamus strictus*, and *Phyllostachys spp.*, as well as in plants as sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum*), cotton (*Gossypium spp.*), corn (*Zea mays*), and grape (*Vitis spp.*). However, it is uncertain to define at what stage of the lifecycle of the beetle it was found in most of these hosts. Thus, it is not known if the action of the beetle has been identified in these larvae stage plants, damaging them, or in the adult stage, where the beetle would only feed of the flower, playing a role as a pollinator. Until now, it is uncertain to define the global geographic distribution of this beetle. The literature cites the incidence of the longhorn beetle *C. annularis* for the continents of Asia (China, India, Indonesia, Japan), Oceania (Australia and New Zealand), America (Brazil and United States), and Europe (France and Spain) (Wang et al., 2017). The lifecycle of *C. annularis* consists of the stages from egg to larvae, and pupae to the adult stage, as shown in Figures 1 and 2. The longhorn beetle lifecycle has a total period of approximately 10 to 12 months of duration, each one with particularities and distinct one from another concerning morphology habitat, and diet. The egg is inoculated on dried bamboo culms by the female (Pest Alert Organization, 2000), who introduces them through a bite on the outer surface of the nodes of the bamboo culms for the posterior inoculation of the eggs on the bamboo nodes. The bite of the beetle is not visible to the naked eye and can only be observed with the use of optical instruments. The larvae stage is characterized by a white coloring cream with a maximum length of 23 mm (Wang et al., 2017), as can be seen in Figures 1b and 1c. The larvae stage can be observed between the outer wall and the inner wall of the bamboo culms. It feeds on the lignocellulosic material of the culm, leaving traces of tunnels full of excrement behind its

OBJECTIVE

The objective of the present paper is to investigate the loss of resistance of Moso bamboo culms infected by the longhorn beetle *Chlorophorus annularis* under concentric compression forces. The experimental work aims to study the relation between the degree of infection due to *C. annularis* in bamboo full-culms and its influence on the physical and mechanical behavior of selected specimens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this work, the mechanical behavior under concentric compression of dried bamboo culms was compared for three different conditions: i) healthy samples; ii) lightly damaged by the infection of *C. annularis* (degree 1), and iii) severely damaged by the beetle infection (degree 2). Three specimens for each condition were produced and tested. The materials and methods adopted are described in the following subsections.

Materials and conditioning

The material used in the present research was *Phyllostachys edulis* bamboo species harvested from a cultivated plantation located in the city of Guarulhos, at the São Paulo State, Brazil (23°21'35.32" S and 46°27'39.09" W), situated 886 m above the sea level. Since the maximal mechanical performance of *P. edulis* bamboo is reached after 3 years old, the Brazilian Code recommends 5-years-old bamboo culms to be used for structural applications (ABNT, 2020). In the present work, Moso bamboo culms harvested at 5 years of age were used and smoke-treated in a horizontal kiln for 72 hours. The culms had a mean diameter of 100 mm, a wall thickness of 10 mm (± 1 mm), and the equilibrium moisture content of samples about 12%. After being cut and treated, the healthy bamboo was exposed to the beetle lifecycle in a workplace with a considerable amount of cut and dried bamboo culms infected by the longhorn beetle, a favorable environment for the breeding of *Chlorophorus annularis*. During the study, it was observed that a single *P. edulis* bamboo culm measuring 90mm diameter on average and 6 meters long may produce more than 21 longhorn beetles during the summer period. The physical and mechanical properties for healthy *P. edulis* culms were obtained by (Seixas *et al.*, 2017), as follows: specific weight of 7.8 kN/m³, the tensile elastic modulus of 20 GPa, the compressive elastic modulus of 15 GPa, shear modulus of 8 MPa, a tensile strength of 180 MPa, the compression strength of 60 MPa and bending modulus of 13 GPa, with a standard deviation within 10%.

Preparation and classification of samples

The samples adopted for mechanical testing were extracted from the middle part of Moso bamboo culms, according to the ISO 22157-1:2004 Code (International Standard, 2004). All samples were cut from the internode region of the culm and had a length of 200 mm, i.e. twice the size of the culm outer diameter, as presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Healthy bamboo culm sample measuring 200 x 100mm (height x diameter)

The degree of damage of each sample varies because it depends on the number of larvae inside the selected segment and the degree of damage caused by the beetle. Bamboo, as a biological material, already has a significant level of complexity regarding its standardization, and to establish the degree

of damage by *C. annularis* for each sample would be no different. To simplify testing and evaluation of results, six damaged samples were selected and divided into only two groups with degrees of damage measured using the calculation of density loss. For this calculation, it was assumed that the original density of the infected samples would correspond to that of healthy samples. Up to 1/6 of the density loss, the samples were classified as lightly damaged (degree 1). Above that, the samples were classified as severely damaged (degree 2). Infected specimens classified according to their degree of damage are presented in Figure 4. In all, nine samples were tested, three of them extracted from healthy bamboo culms and three for each group of damaged samples. The ends of the specimens were sanded to avoid stress concentration and eccentricities during the mechanical tests. Moreover, the damaged samples received an epoxy resin treatment at the ends to seal the holes produced by the insect. This procedure aimed to avoid localized rupture and, thus, compromise the results of the mechanical tests.

Figure 4: Infected bamboo samples classified according to degree of damage: degree 1 in yellow and degree 2 in red

Mechanical tests

Compression tests were performed with a Controls 50-C46Z00 / MCC8 Multitest testing machine with a capacity of 2000kN. The tests were performed until rupture, with displacement control at a loading rate of 0.6mm/min. Axial deformations were obtained through displacement transducers coupled to acrylic rings fixed to the specimen and 165mm apart, as shown in Figure 5a.

Discussion of the results

The rupture of the healthy samples was characterized by the formation of longitudinal splitting cracks, i.e. parallel to the fiber direction. The literature reports that fracture occurs in the parenchyma cells domain, a cellulosic material present between the fibers, usually with a filling function and that has less mechanical resistance (Akinbade & Harries, 2021). Figure 5b illustrates the cracks at the end of a healthy bamboo culm sample after the mechanical test.

a) Set-up adopted for the compression test.

b) Failure mode of the healthy bamboo samples after the compression test

Figure 5: Mechanical test

Before the appearance of the first cracks, a bulging shape was observed near the base of the healthy samples, as shown in Figure 6a. Then, the first cracks form at the base and propagate towards the top of the sample, as shown in Figure 6b. Even after the failure, bamboo maintained this deformed configuration. Figure 6c shows a typical bamboo sample and its longitudinal cracks after the mechanical test.

a) bulging shape near the base indicated by red arrows

b) formation of longitudinal splitting cracks indicated by blue arrows

c) failure mode with longitudinal cracks along specimen length

Figure 6: Typical compression test of a healthy bamboo sample

Damaged samples resisted significantly less than the healthy samples, forming cracks in the first seconds of testing, before exhibiting a deformed bulging shape. Cracks started near the ends towards the center or the opposite. This path followed the channels visible by the holes in the outer surface of the bamboo culm, as shown in Figure 7. It was observed that the holes were the starting point of the cracks during the mechanical test.

Figure 7: Compression test of the degree 2 damaged bamboo sample: (a) deformation of the damaged bamboo sample during the mechanical test. (b) specimen without the outer shell after rupture

The comparison can be done in terms of the stress x strain for specimens, as shown in Figure 8. For all specimens, a gross cross-sectional area of 2800 mm^2 was considered. The measured values for compressive strength and modulus of elasticity of the healthy samples were, respectively, 54 MPa and 14 GPa. It can be highlighted that these results are in agreement with previously reported properties (Seixas *et al.*, 2017). The results obtained from the degree 1 damaged samples indicate a different mechanical behavior from healthy samples during the mechanical test. A load drop was observed near 30 MPa, which characterizes the collapse of the bamboo culm structure, followed by a plateau associated with residual stress carried by the undamaged portion of the culm after stress redistribution. In the plateau, successive small load drops can be observed, each one associated with a localized failure. Such a level of damage for the culms demonstrates a loss of compressive strength of approximately 25 MPa and MOE of 9.5 GPa for the analyzed samples. The degree 2 damaged samples showed the highest number of consecutive ruptures due to the larger number of channels arranged in the material culm wall. Its compressive strength presented extremely low values, exhibiting a strength of about 15% of that observed for healthy samples and MOE 11.1 GPa lower.

Figure 8: Stress-strain relationships for tested specimens

CONCLUSION

The Cerambycid beetle *Chlorophorus annularis* (Fabricius) is a problem for the round pole bamboo industry and the dissemination of bamboo structures on a larger scale in Brazil and other countries such as China, India, and the USA. The presented study investigated the presence of the longhorn beetle in *Phyllostachys edulis* bamboo culms at the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro PUC-Rio. The authors studied the relation between the degree of infection of *C. annularis* in Moso bamboo culms and its influence on the physical and mechanical behavior of selected samples. Three different categories were established for compression mechanical tests: i) healthy samples, ii) lightly damaged samples, and iii) severely damaged samples (degree 2). Nine samples were produced, subdivided into

three samples for each category. It was observed a loss of mass in the selected samples damaged by *C. annularis*. The preparation of the samples considered that up to 1/6 of the density loss, the samples were classified as the degree of damage level 1. Above that, the samples were classified as the degree of damage level 2. Concentric compression tests were realized using a Controls 50-C46Z00 / MCC8 Multitest machine. The results obtained by the mechanical tests on healthy samples were 54 MPa for compression and 14 GPa for modulus of elasticity (MOE) values. The results obtained from the lightly damaged samples degree 1 showed a different mechanical behavior from the tested healthy samples. The first rupture can be observed near 30 MPa, which demonstrates the failure of the culm structure. The level of damaged degree 1 shows a loss of compressive strength of approximately 25 MPa. The MOE value observed for the damaged samples degree level 1 was 9.5 GPa for the analyzed samples. The severely damaged samples degree 2 showed consecutive fractures of the samples. Its compressive strength shows very low values, showing a resistance below 15% of those observed in healthy samples and MOE of 11.1 GPa for the analyzed samples. The authors conclude the importance of the treatment of Moso bamboo culms against *Chlorophorus annularis* longhorn beetle. The treatment will also need the monitoring of the bamboo culms at PUC-Rio laboratories and the propagation lifecycle of the beetle year after year. Traps and isolation chambers for bamboo culms are being developed at the University to generate more accurate information about the longhorn beetle lifecycle and methods for controlling the proliferation of *Chlorophorus annularis* in Moso bamboo.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.